

CHARACTERIZATION OF BRAZILIAN COMMERCIAL CLAYS AND APPLICATION IN THE REMOVAL OF Cu^{2+} FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS

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RESUMO

Foi investigada a capacidade de argilas comerciais brasileiras na remoção de Cu^{2+} de soluções aquosas. Foram estudados diversos parâmetros: pré-tratamento da argila, tempo de contato, diferentes concentrações iniciais de cobre e natureza dos sais de cobre. Os resultados mostraram que as argilas comerciais estudadas foram efetivas na remoção de cobre de soluções aquosas em poucos minutos. Em soluções diluídas, o pré-tratamento ou o tipo de sal de cobre não tiveram influência na capacidade de adsorção. Por outro lado, em soluções concentradas os melhores resultados foram obtidos na presença de nitrato de cobre. As características estruturais das argilas comerciais e das argilas intercaladas com cobre foram determinadas por DRX e RMN no Estado Sólido.

Palavras-chave: *argilominerais, metais pesados, soluções aquosas, tratamento de efluentes.*

ABSTRACT

The Brazilian commercial acid clay capacity to remove Cu^{2+} from aqueous solutions was investigated. Pretreatment of clay, initial copper concentrations, contact time and kind of copper salts, namely chloride, nitrate and sulfate were studied. The results show that the clay was effective in removing the copper from aqueous solutions in few minutes. In the dilute solutions, the clay pretreatment or type of copper salts had no influence on the capacity of adsorption. On the other hand, in the concentrated solutions, the better result was obtained in the presence of copper nitrate. The structural characteristics of the commercial and intercalated Cu-clays were determined by XRD and Solid State NMR.

Keywords: *clay minerals, heavy metals, aqueous solutions, wastewater treatment*

Introduction

Industrial wastewaters contain, frequently, high levels of heavy metals and treatment is needed before disposal, in order to avoid water pollution. Numerous processes exist for removing dissolved heavy metals, including ion exchange, precipitation, phyto-extraction, ultrafiltration, reverse osmosis and electrodialysis (Applegate, 1999; Sengputa et al., 1986; Mier et al., 2001; Tuzena et al., 2006; Weng et al., 2007). Nevertheless, many of these approaches can be marginally cost-effective or difficult to implement in developing countries. Therefore, the need exists for a treatment strategy that is simple, efficient and inexpensive. In this regard, naturally occurring clays hold great potential for use as adsorbent material to remove heavy metals from industrial wastewater (Aguiar et al., 2002; Miranda-Trevino et al., 2003).

Smectite, that is often dominant clay in soils formed, is hydrated aluminum silicates with very fine particle size, usually $< 2\mu\text{m}$. It has layered structure formed by two tetrahedral sheets linked to an octahedral sheet through sharing of apical oxygens. The tetrahedral contain mainly Si(IV) as the central atom, while the octahedral sites are occupied mostly by Al(III) but partly substituted with Fe(III) and Mg(II) (Grim, 1968).

Modification of properties of natural materials is recognized as an attractive approach for possible use of these materials as adsorbents for heavy metal removal (Jiang et al., 2003). An understanding of the characteristic and adsorption mechanisms is crucial for clays potential application. Hence, the aim of this work is to investigate the structural features of a Brazilian commercial acid clay (smectite like) in presence of Cu^{2+} aqueous solution.

Materials and Methods

One commercial acid Brazilian clay (smectite like) with 218 m^2 of surface area was donated by Bentonit do Brasil. Standard metal solutions of known concentrations were prepared employed different copper salts (Merck): $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The pretreatment of the clay consisted in the washing of the commercial clay was thoroughly washed with distilled water to remove the

adhering dust and dried in an oven at 100°C using different time of heating (1, 2 or 3 hours).

Adsorption studies: Batch adsorption experiments were carried out, in triplicate, by shaking 1,25 g of the commercial acid clay with 25,0 mL aqueous Cu^{2+} solutions of 6 to 600 mg L^{-1} at $35 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$. At the end of the time interval, the clay was removed by centrifugation at 3000 rpm during 10 minutes, washed with deionized water and the copper amount was measured employed 3000 Perkin Elmer Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer apparatus using an air acetylene flame. The sorbed copper amount was the difference between the initial amount and the amount remaining in solution. The solution pH before and after copper adsorption were 4,0 and 3,5-3,0, respectively.

Characterization of the clays: The clay chemical composition was determined by X-ray fluorescence using a Philips 1.480 with Rh tub. The X-ray diffractions (XRD) of oriented samples were conducted using a RIGAKU MINIFLEX diffractometer equipped with a proportional counter and pulse height analyser Ni filtered by $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation at 30 kV and 15 mA. Diffraction patterns were collected at a scanning rate of $1^\circ (2\theta)/\text{min}$ in the interval of 2° and 30° . Solid state NMR measurements were carried out on a Bruker Avance, DRX-300 spectrometer operating at a B_0 of 7.05 Tesla, corresponding to a Larmor frequency of 78.2 MHz for aluminum and 59.6 MHz for silicon. Samples were spun in zirconia's rotors equipped with Kel-F caps, at speed of 12 kHz. A short pulse of 7 μs was used and the recycle time was 0.3 s, for ^{27}Al , while the ^{29}Si pulse was of 10 μs and its recycle time was 0,5 s. The ^{27}Al chemical shifts were referenced using a solid sample of $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\delta = 0$ ppm), while the ^{29}Si signal positions were referenced using a secondary standard of caulim ($\delta = -91.5$ ppm) in relation to TMS.

Results and Discussion

The chemical composition of the commercial acid Brazilian smectite was showed in Table 1. The observed high Si/Al ratio (10,28) has evidenced that the acid treatment made by the Brazilian Company provoked an attack on the natural smectite structure. Probably, this treatment has caused the dissolution of aluminum oxide of the sites octahedral of the natural clay

(Kumar et al., 1995).

The influence of copper concentration and the treatment of clay (heating at 100°C in different times), on the sorption by clay were investigated. Figure 1 shows that the copper adsorption percentage remains constant, independent upon the clay pretreatment. Hence, the clay was not pretreated in all subsequent measurements. It was also observed that at lower concentration (6 mg L⁻¹) the copper removal was almost complete compared to the other ones.

Figure 1 - Effect of heating at 100°C during the pretreatment on the clay capacity adsorption to removal Cu²⁺ (Test conditions: contact time: 10 min; [Cu²⁺]_i, mg L⁻¹: ■ = 600; ▲ = 60; ◆ = 6)

The influence of contact time and suspension shaking on copper sorption were evaluated. As it can be seen in Figure 2, the equilibrium of copper removal has reached within the contact time of 10 minutes under stirring. On the other hand, in the experiment without stirring, the equilibrium is not reached even after 1.440 minutes. In this condition, the equilibrium was only reached at 2.960 min (not shown). Hence, the suspension stirring has an important role on the sorption process.

Figure 2 - Effect of contact time and stirring of suspensions on the adsorption of Cu²⁺ onto commercial Brazilian clay: ■: with stirred; ▲: without stirring. (Test conditions: [Cu²⁺]_i: 6 mg L⁻¹)

The copper solution concentration and salt copper type have a strong effect on metal speciation and consequently in its removal efficiency. It is well known that cationic metal species are more efficiently removed by ion exchange process using acid clays (Stadler et al, 1993). Figure 3 shows the copper salt effect on the sorption by untreated clay. In diluted solutions (6 mg L⁻¹), the copper salt kind had no influence on the copper sorption. (poderia ser melhor explorado a adsorção não proporcional em relação à concentração de cobre)

Figure 3 - Effect of copper salt kind and its initial concentration on Cu²⁺ removal by clay. (Test conditions: pH=4.0, contact time= 10 min.) (■: NO₃⁻; ◆: SO₄²⁻; ▲: Cl⁻)

This fact is due to, in these conditions the predominant copper species are [Cu(H₂O)₆]²⁺ independent upon employed salt. On the other hand, in higher initial concentrations (above 60 mg L⁻¹), it was observed an increasing of Cu²⁺ removal which was dependent upon copper salt kind. These results could be explained by the hard-soft acid base principle (HSAB). Cations and ligands are generally Lewis acids and bases, respectively, of different strengths: for example, alkali metal cations are hard, Zn²⁺ and Cu²⁺ are borderline and Hg and Ag⁺ are soft acids, while SO₄²⁻ and NO₃⁻ are hard, Br is borderline and I⁻ are soft. Hard acids prefer to bind with hard Lewis bases and soft acids prefer to bind with soft bases (Pearson, 1968). In this case, as the Cl⁻ is less hard than SO₄²⁻ or NO₃⁻, it is competing with the mineral surface for the borderline acid Cu²⁺, so more of the Cu²⁺ remains in solution. The excess negative charge in montmorillonite due to isomorphous substitution is spread between the tetrahedral and octahedral within the crystal. The location of layer charge in smectite determines the strength of the clay ligand and can affect the

selectivity of metals: smectite behaves as a soft base when the layer charge is located in the octahedral sites, while it behaves as a hard base when the charge is located in the tetrahedral sheet (Xu et al., 1992). It follows that charge located in montmorillonite would be predominantly located in the octahedral sheet (Puls et al., 1988).

The crystalline configuration and the basal spacing of the clays can be identified by XRD spectra. The Table 2 shows the $d(001)$ reflections for the oriented samples. The untreated clay showed a broad peak at 14.7 Å ($2\theta = 5.95^\circ$), confirmed the clay mineral presence of the smectite group. In all clays, was observed the presence of a large peak at 26.9 Å ($2\theta = 3.31^\circ$) suggesting the presence of quartz in this material (Grim, 1968). The values $d(001)$ Cu-clay (15.8 Å) was larger than $d(001)$ raw material (14.7 Å), where the interlayer region is mostly Ca^{+2} and Na^+ populated. This behavior is probably due to a stronger interaction between hard-alkali and earth-alkali metals acids and the hard base (H_2O). In addition, the Cu-clay XRD patterns show that the smectite reflection is more enlarged in the Cu-clay prepared with $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution, indicating that the framework was disarranged than in the others clay minerals. This result confirms that the copper was more easily anchored into clay structure when the copper nitrate was used. On the other hands, in the clay intercalated with CuSO_4 solution, this peak presents more resolution than the others samples. Therefore, this solution causes less damage in the clay framework than the others ones.

Table 2 - The $d(001)$ reflections (Å) of raw and Cu- clays

Sample	$d(001)$
Commercial clay	14.7
Cu-Clay in NO_3^-	15.8
Cu-Clay in SO_4^{2-}	14.9
Cu-Clay in Cl^-	14.8

The ^{27}Al MAS-NMR spectra of the clay samples are shown in Figure 4. The spectra shows two principal components and a series of sidebands associated to the spinning of the samples. The line around 0 ppm is related to octahedral sites and the line at 56 ppm to tetrahedral Al ions (Engelhardt et al., 1997). For ^{27}Al nuclei, large variations of the quadrupole

coupling constant provokes distortion of the peak shape and sideband pattern because of the influence increasing of second-order terms (Thompson, J.G., 1984).

Figure 4 - ^{27}Al MAS NMR spectra of the samples. The spinning sidebands are labeled*. (1. acid clay; 2. Cu-Clay in SO_4^{2-} ; 3. Cu-Clay in NO_3^- ; 4. Cu-Clay in Cl^-)

In all the clay studied, the ^{27}Al MAS NMR spectra show the presence of tetrahedral aluminum (Al^{IV}) and octahedral (Al^{VI}) sites. In untreated clay, the Al^{IV} and Al^{VI} contents are 10% and 90%, respectively (Table 3).

Table 3 - Percentual composition of tetrahedral and octahedral aluminum in the clays

Clay	% Al^{IV}	% Al^{VI}
Natural clay ¹	7	93
Commercial clay	10	90
Cu-Clay in NO_3^-	15	85
Cu-Clay in SO_4^{2-}	10	90
Cu-Clay in Cl^-	10	90

Font: The Brazilian natural smectite precursor of acid commercial clay (Guarino et al., 1997).

After intercalation with $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution, the smaller Al^{VI} content (85%) was reached compared to the others. This result suggests that the copper ions anchor preferentially into the octahedral framework, provoking aluminum removal. Guarino et al. (1997) have studied a

Brazilian natural smectite precursor of this commercial clay (Table 3). This clay has presented 7.0% of Al^{IV} and 93.0% of Al^{VI} (Guarino et al., 1997). The higher content of Al^{VI} in natural clay compared with commercial acid indicated the process of dealumination, while the Al^{IV} content remains constant. The Al^{IV} bound in three-dimensional framework is rather stable against acid attack, so it remains in the structure of final product (Tkáč et al., 1994).

Figure 5 shows the ²⁹Si MAS NMR spectra of commercial acid clay and the clay intercalated with Cu(NO₃)₂ solution. The ²⁹Si chemical shift (ppm) of the main peak displays at -92.7 to -94.1 ppm corresponding to (Q³ nAl) sites, which it's according to data about smectites (Engelhardt et al., 1997). The signal around -107.8 ppm corresponds to (Q⁴ 0Al) α-quartz sites. At -110 ppm, there is a signal that corresponds to amorphous silica. This signal was not observed in Brazilian natural clay (Guarino et al., 1997). Therefore, it suggests that amorphous silica was generated during acid treatment.

Figure 5 - ²⁹Si MAS NMR spectra of acid clay (1) and clay intercalated with Cu(NO₃)₂ solution (2).

Conclusions

The use of Brazilian commercial acid clay has great potential for copper removal from aqueous solution. The optimal conditions for Cu²⁺ removal are: non treated clay, using diluted solution containing nitrate ions and using stirring during few minutes. The NMR and XRD analyses have showed that the presence of nitrate counterion in aqueous solution has provoked more damage in clay framework due to more Cu²⁺ anchoring into the clay structure.

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Table 1 - Chemical composition of commercial acid Brazilian smectite (wt%)

SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	MgO	CaO	TiO ₂	P ₂ O ₅	CuO
83,91	8,16	3,95	0,15	0,51	1,06	0,96	1,23	0,06	0,01